

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ORAL METHOD IN FORMING IMAGINATIONS ABOUT NATURE IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific-theoretical importance and foundations of forming children's ideas about nature through the oral method.

Key words: methodology, oral method, nature, educational system, theory.

Introduction.

One of the main types of oral method is a story. It is combined with reading books, showing objects and events, using technical tools, reading fiction, etc.

The story tells strictly about tracking. Types of story telling or description, characterization, explanation, discussion are used in nature classes.

Telling - it tells about a concrete fact, event, process, actions. The story is told on behalf of an eyewitness (*a tourist, a young naturalist, a traveler, a participant in discoveries*).

Description is the existence of objects and the story is conducted on behalf of the witness (*tourist, young naturalist, traveler, participant of discoveries*).

Description is used in the consistent description of existing bodies and phenomena (*minerals, plants, animal world, climatic features of a natural zone*).

Characterization is a type of description, which consists in listing the signs and properties of an object or phenomenon (*characteristics of mountains, rivers, and natural zones*).

Explanation - it reveals new concepts, terms, meaning, cause and effect connection, the logical nature of this or that thing (*why there is long night and short day in the tundra, why day and night, seasons alternately*) will be revealed. It is used in all lessons, and it is combined with discussion.

Discussion is based on the statement, and it is related to the consistent development of rules and evidence that lead students to a conclusion. This type of story is used when there is a need to analyze the phenomenon being studied (*for example, the effect of climate on the change of a living being, properties of water, metal*).

It is important to use the following didactic methods during the story:

I. Announcing the topic of the lesson, a problematic situation is created before the introduction of a new topic. It begins with studying or experimenting with new material, as well as analyzing observations made in nature.

II. Communicate the narrative plan. This method not only activates the process of mastering, but also teaches students to see the entire narrative system, thereby helping to develop the logical consistency of thinking, to identify certain connections between the facts

or events of the studied environment; for example, describing the topic "The nature of the desert", the educator can write this plan on the board:

- 1) *the geographical location of deserts on the map of natural zones;*
- 2) *features of the desert climate;*
- 3) *surface;*
- 4) *oases;*
- 5) *seasons in the desert.*

III. Asking questions that activate the attention of students during the presentation.

IV. Activating comparison of students' cognitive activities (*for example, comparing flora and fauna of fields, deserts, steppes, forests, etc.*).

V. During the presentation of the new material, to study the connection of previously studied topics with life and practice (*for example, the topic "Skeleton" with the topic "Muscles", the nature of the countryside with the topic of the nature of various zones*) in life, practice .

VI. Include a proverb, interesting material, or reading episode in the story.

The teacher can start the story after reading the relevant article or before. The use of additional material enriches and concretizes the story. The proverbs, sayings and riddles used during the story enrich the lesson and make it easier for the pupils to accept the material being presented.

VII. Use of visualization (*photo, table, technical tools*). The use of various means of visualization during the story will help students to form clear images, to support attention and interest in the studied material, and to master it thoroughly. experiments, blackboards and notebooks (*terms*) and conclusions facilitate the learning of educational material.

Conversation. The conversation is characterized by the participation of students and teachers in solving the question. The focus of the conversation is determined by the questions that must be solved by mobilizing the knowledge of the students. As a result of the conversation, under the guidance of the teacher, the students should make appropriate conclusions and summarize the conclusions. The conversation should not be unfamiliar to the trainees: it is not appropriate to waste time trying to "find out" the knowledge that the trainees have not mastered yet. Conversation is of particular importance in lessons that conclude, generalize and connect new knowledge with old ones.

The main purpose of the conversation is that, under the guidance of the teacher, correct ideas and concepts about natural objects and phenomena are formed in the minds of the students. At the first stage of introduction to nature, the conversation takes place in the form of the educator asking questions and the students who called him answering the questions. Then the conversation will be enriched and expanded.

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